

Developing an AR application for self-exploration at the Roman Temple in Antiochia ad Cragum, Turkey

Mamoli Myrsini^{*1}, Erdogmus Ece², Townsend Rhys³, Ben Kreimer⁴

¹ Georgia Institute of Technology – Atlanta, GA

² Clemson University – Clemson, SC

³ Clarke University – Worcester, MA

⁴ Volumn – Lincoln, NE

*Corresponding author

Correspondence: myrsini@gatech.edu

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a VR and an AR mobile applications, developed for the physical and remote self-navigation of the public at the NE Temple in Antiochia ad Cragum in Southern Turkey, built in the late 2nd/early 3rd c. CE. The goal of the applications is to demystify archaeological research and combat the public perception of non-discrete, unidentifiable remains in archaeological sites, as commonly summarized as “just stones”. The temple has collapsed due to an earthquake, but most of its building material survives on site, and it’s an excellent didactic example of Roman stone-cut temple architecture. The paper presents the methodology of digitally capturing in-situ building remains and a sample of disiecta membra using LiDAR scanning, digitally documenting it in 2D orthogonal state of preservation drawings, inferring their reconstruction, and putting it all together to build virtually the 3d model of the whole temple. creating a high-accuracy reconstruction model of the temple. In the second half, the paper explores the range of digital applications that can present this model and the research behind it and gives preliminary results of testing these applications.

Keywords: Digital documentation, LiDAR scanning, 3D reconstruction, point cloud, Roman Temple, Architecture, VR/AR

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Introduction

39 The so-called “NE Temple” in Antiochia ad Cragum, a Roman city on the south coast of Turkey,
40 has been excavated since 2005. The excavations have uncovered the remains of the city, along
41 the important Cilician road, developed in terraces on the slopes of the mountain, that included a
42 monumental colonnaded agora, a main street with a gate, a theater, two bathing complexes, and
43 temples. Among the building remains, the most intriguing and the earliest to be studied was a
44 tetrastyle prostyle podium temple, perched over the Roman city at its northeastern side, with a
45 great vista to the Acropolis and the principal civic buildings of the city (figure 1). This was a highly-
46 visibly temple, fully cut in stone, with a plethora of sculptural details, probably dedicated at the end
47 of the 2nd c. – beginning of the 3rd c. CE.

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49 **Figure 1** – View of the Temple from the NE corner, the view from the temple to the
50 Hellenistic Acropolis, and the center of the city; and topographic map of Antiochia
51 ad Cragum showing temple in red and the sightlines towards the Acropolis and the
52 principal monuments.

53 The temple was repurposed into a burial ground in the Byzantine period until it collapsed due
54 to an earthquake till the level of its stylobate. Additionally, a wine press was developed on its flanks
55 taking advantage of its ready building material.

56 The course of the excavations uncovered the building remains of the temple, cleaned and
57 positioned more than 600 building blocks on the surrounding field, that are estimated to constitute
58 about the 80% of the building materials of the temple (figure 2).

59 The temple is a minor provincial temple, left incomplete, with its different blocks sculpted with
60 various levels of craftsmanship, and evidence of very few clamps to keep it together. Still, the
61 degree of its preservation elevates it to a very didactic example about its building construction, that
62 can serve both the architectural historians' community and the public alike.

63 In this paper I present the process of its digital documentation and reconstruction using the in-
64 situ building remains and a sample of blocks from the disiect membra to restore its geometry in a
65 3d puzzle, and the development of two educational VR/AR applications that synthesize the state
66 of preservation and the reconstruction, the evidence and the hypothesis, and invites the public to
67 explore the blocks and learn about their placement and role in the architecture of the temple, in a
68 similar way to previous work with the Library of Nysa (Mamoli 2007). Thus, the public can self-
69 navigate the site, explore the blocks, gain insights into the archaeological scholarly arguments,
70 and thus be active readers and learners of the material record, according to the principles
71 established by the Charter of London for digital reconstructions (Denard 2021).

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75 **Figure 2** – Orthographic view of the site including the in situ remains at the lower
 76 right corner and the over 600 disiecta membra, cleaned and set on either side of the
 77 path (Image source: Courtesy of Antiochia ad Cragum Archaeological Research
 78 Project).

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Methodology

80 Digital data capturing.

81 For the data reconnaissance of the in-situ building remains of the temple as well as of a sample
 82 of 30 building blocks, on which the reconstruction of the temple is based, we used three different
 83 methods of LiDAR scanning for the different scales of the site: drone photography for the
 84 landscape and the urban scale; faro focus terrestrial scanner for the in-situ remains; and polycam
 85 with an iphone for the individual building blocks (figure 3).

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87 **Figure 3** – Three methods of LiDAR scanning in three different scales: drone for the
 88 landscape (Ben Kreimer, volum), terrestrial scanner for the in situ remains (Botao
 89 Li, Georgia Tech); and polycam with an iphone Pro for the disiecta membra (author).

90 Digital documentation of Disiecta membra: state of preservation and reconstruction.

91 Once we had the point clouds of the different blocks and the platform, we imported them in
 92 Rhino and processed them following standard architectural methodologies used in the
 93 documentation of historical architecture. We traced the meshes of the 3d scanned blocks to
 94 produce 2D orthographic state of preservation drawings. In this process, we compared our
 95 observations with the archaeological drawings made by hand with analogue measurements, to
 96 identify misidentified parts that in some cases are more visible in the naked eye. Using the 2D
 97 state of preservation drawings, we inferred and extrapolated the restored geometry of the blocks
 98 prior to fractures or weathering. These steps along with a table of analyzed blocks are given in
 99 figure 4.

100

1 tracing the building block

2. comparing the drawings with the analogue drawings, Troubleshooting and improving the drawings

3. inferring the reconstruction from the state of preservation

4. 3D modelling the block based on the 2d plan, elevations and section

State of Preservation	Reconstruction Orthographics	State of Preservation	Reconstruction Orthographics
<p>AT191: Right Corner Gelson</p>	<p>gelson-moulding and cavetto-compositum</p>	<p>AT290+292: Pilaster Upper Block</p>	
<p>AT429: Frieze</p>		<p>AT422-115: Pilaster Base</p>	
<p>AT186: Frieze</p>		<p>AT119: Aedicula Pediment</p>	
<p>AT421: Architrave</p>		<p>AT551 + 091: Door Lintel</p>	
<p>AT173: Column Capital</p>		<p>AT554: Door Jamb</p>	
<p>AT175: Column Drum</p>		<p>AT638: Podium Moulding</p>	
<p>AT067: Ionic Column Base</p>		<p>AT160: Corinthian Anta Capital (left)</p>	
<p>AT159: Antae Block</p>		<p>AT098</p>	
<p>AT085: Antae Base (Left)</p>		<p>Measurement of Pilaster Corner Angles</p>	

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Digital documentation of in situ remains: state of preservation and reconstruction.

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We followed the same methodology for the scale of the whole temple platform, treating it as an oversized building block. We produced the state of preservation and reconstruction drawings of the podium platform, establishing the invariable evidence of the temple: the overall dimensions and geometry of the podium platform, and the basic dimensions of the temple based on the dimensions and the steps of the podium, the in-situ back wall of the cella, and the cella threshold (Figure 5). The technology gave us an important advantage in creating these drawings. By being able to use clipping plane commands, we were able to trace multiple sections of the platform very

113 easily, and thus establish the heights of the important features: the cella threshold and floor, and
114 back wall, as well as the crepis of the podium and identify blocks in the fragmentary front as being
115 at the same height, therefore as co-belonging to the crepis, and thus establishing the southern
116 boundary of the temple.

117

118 **Figure 5** - Synthesis of the state of preservation and the reconstruction drawings
119 for the platform of the temple.

120 **Synthesis of the restored geometry of temple podium with the restored geometry of the**
121 **sample blocks.**

122 Once we had the 3d reconstruction models of all components of the temple, our next step was
123 to put them together, thus completing a 3D puzzle of the temple, as it was probably designed in
124 the 2nd – 3rd centuries CE.

125 This step proved quite challenging, because the temple and each block of it is an object fully sculpted
126 by hand, therefore its measurements are not always precise, especially in a rushed provincial temple, as
127 the subject of our project.

128 Several problems in the reconstruction of the temple that were identified with analogue methods,
129 with this technology were exacerbated, as the medium allowed their full visualization. The question
130 arose how we would reconstruct the temple: as it was conceptualized or as it was built? On one hand,
131 our goal was to stay truthful to the evidence, on the other side, when the measurements even within the
132 same block varied, we had to abstract and generalize the evidence and use measurements on average.
133 Soon enough it became clear that we had to follow a combination of these methods, otherwise we would
134 be trapped into minor variations of the evidence that we couldn't even justify as coincidental or
135 intentional. Ultimately, this goal is the goal of the archaeologist and was beyond the goals of our project
136 which was the education of the public. While the building clearly deviates from a fully orthogonal
137 geometry, we chose to reconstruct it as such (figure 6), not taking into account these deviations, for the
138 sake of time, and also to leave this question to the archaeological publication to answer first.

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Figure 6 – Different views of the reconstruction of the temple superimposed on the point cloud of the preserved in-situ remains.

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Presentation of the Synthesis of Evidence and Hypothesis.

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Once the model of the temple is completed, there is a variety of ways one can present it, based on the goals each time. The most straightforward one for archaeological research and museum studies is exporting any kind of isometric drawings or renderings, appropriate to be used in any print material, from academic publications to museum boards in the museum or the archaeological site. Virtual environments and augmented reality environments that allow the synthesis of the point cloud of the in-situ remains and the state of reconstruction of the temple in real time, offer an additional level of interactivity, and engagement of the public. Here we develop two applications to navigate this synthesis, a VR and an AR mobile application, that allow the self-navigation of the public on site and remotely to understand the evidence among the hypothesis, while maintaining the same rigor as in publications with traditional print media, according to the principles established by the Charter of London for digital reconstructions (Denard 2021). These are described in detail in the next section.

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Project Outcomes

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Mobile AR App

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A mobile application for the self-navigation of the public on site. Visitors to the temple will be able to access the application by scanning select building blocks with their phones and accessing information about their proposed reconstruction. Thus, they will be able to navigate the site and participate in the research argument made and be active readers and learners of the material record, and not passive recipients of ready-made information.

We developed this prototype application, and we tested it on campus at Georgia Tech. Since we are remotely and did not have the actual preserved block in front of us, we used a 3d printed

165 model in scale 1:20 and followed the navigation in reverse order, i.e. from reconstruction to state
166 of preservation. The app recognized the 3d printed model and popped up the preserved scanned
167 block.

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169 **Figure 7** – AR mobile app that synthesizes the evidence and hypothesis, the
170 reconstructed model of the anta capital and the scanned preserved block on site.

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172 On site, the opposite will happen: the user will recognize the original block and pop up the
173 reconstruction. In both cases:

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- The user can manipulate the block to see it from different angles
- There is a button that can switch between the two states: state of preservation and reconstruction
- There are two buttons that control the modes of information: one gives text with information about the function of the block and its placement on the temple, and the other drawings that document its details and different views, as well as the placement of the block on the temple.

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This example shows block AT638, which is a front block of the podium.

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183 **Figure 8** – AR mobile app that allows the self-navigation of the public. The interface offers three
 184 functionalities: 1. To rotate the block and observe it carefully from different angles; 2) navigate among
 185 the two states: the state of preservation (scanned block) and the reconstruction of the bloc; 3) navigate
 186 among two modes of info, text and visual with orthographic drawings of the block as well as the
 187 placement of the block in the temple

188 A preliminary testing of this application on the Georgia Tech campus showed that the
 189 application attracted people of all ages, from children to older adults, who due to the technology
 190 became curious and got engaged with the material at hand.

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192 **Figure 9** – Testing of the application at the End of Year Exhibition, College of Design
 193 Georgia Tech, Atlanta, GA, USA, May 1, 2025.

194 **Vr Environment For Remote Self-Navigation**

195 The second application is a VR environment that includes the same information as the AR
 196 mobile app and is designed to expand the accessibility of the temple online. The environment
 197 includes the blockfield, where the disiecta membra are placed and the in-situ remains of the temple
 198 in their natural surroundings. Users can use a headset for full immersion, or they can just navigate
 199 with the mouse of their computer. Either way, they can navigate on site (using the buttons AWSD

200 for left, forward, backward and right movement), starting from the beginning of the blockfield,
 201 walking towards the temple, simulating the path they would follow visiting the temple physically,
 202 and at the same time admiring the natural landscape with its breathtaking views to the
 203 mediterranean and the complexity of archaeology with the 600 blocks lying around the temple. The
 204 question that arises from this experience naturally is “How do they know which block is what and
 205 how the temple is reconstructed?”

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207 **Figure 10** – Three screenshots showing the functionality of the virtual environment.
 208 A) the user navigates in the archeological site; b) the user can select the
 209 reconstruction of the superstructure of the Temple to appear with transparency,
 210 superimposed on the building remains of the temple; c) the user can select a certain
 211 block, in this example the corner geison block of the front pediment. The user can
 212 inspect the block itself in front of them, read about the thinking process
 213 archaeologists follow in identifying the block and placing it on the temple, and look
 214 at the drawings they produce that show the inference of the reconstruction from the
 215 state of preservation.

216 Users can transition among the “Ruins” and “Reconstruction” mode by clicking T and admire
 217 the restoration of the superstructure of the temple superimposed on the point cloud of the
 218 preserved podium (figure 10). The selected blocks we have worked with are curated and placed

219 right in front of the temple, at the spot of the best view of their restoration. Users can select different
220 blocks in the blockfield to learn more and reason about them. Once the mouse hovers over a
221 selectable block, a green circle appears. With one click, a pop-up window appears with two modes
222 of info: textual and visual, and a duplicate of the scanned state of preservation block appears at
223 its correct place on the temple. The placement of the block in the temple is justified with words in
224 the pop-up window, and the user is invited to observe the block and its carvings and understand
225 why the archaeologists interpret it and the way they do, and what this block tells us about the
226 geometry of the temple.

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Results and Discussion

228 A preliminary presentation of the project has verified our initial hypotheses: 1) the applications
229 are successful in **expanding the public's engagement and the time** spent visiting it by
230 Interrelating the landscape with the temple, and appreciating the whole site, not just the temple; 2)
231 the applications help make the archaeological **research transparent** to the public and ask them
232 to partake in the reconstruction process block-by-block according to the principles of the Charter
233 of London, thus providing the public quality **life-long education** (UN SDG #4), and inspire the
234 public to **advocate** for archaeology as a field and for the preservation of cultural heritage, and
235 ultimately contribute in the development of sustainable tourism in these underrepresented regions,
236 another vehicle for sustainable development. Further, the applications demonstrate that the depth
237 of this exceptionally and largely preserved building material of the temple makes a great case
238 study for **STEM education**, especially in inspiring younger ages.

239 Our future goal remains to work with the Turkish ministry of Culture and the Museum of Alanya
240 that oversees the site and hosts the most important findings in its galleries, to co-curate a
241 circulation path on site that will incorporate museum boards with reconstruction renderings and
242 drawings as well as AR components that the visitors will be able to access through their phones.
243 By putting QR codes to different curated spots around the temple, we make this VR application
244 part of the circulation path of the archaeological site and enable the visitors to access the
245 reconstruction from multiple points of view, experiencing the reconstructed temple within its ruins
246 and the landscape. Additionally, by putting QR codes in select building blocks we extend the
247 visitors' experience to the whole uncovered archaeological record and make the field of building
248 blocks part of the destination, not just an area necessary to cross to reach the destination, which
249 is the temple. Thus, we hope to combat the typical non-expert visitors' perception that
250 archaeological remains are "all stones" and demystify the methodology that archaeologist use in
251 the reconstruction process.

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Conflict of interest disclosure

265 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest
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267

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